

Cloud Computing Support for Diagnosing Researches

Authors : A. Amirov, O. Gerget, V. Kochegurov

Abstract : One of the main biomedical problem lies in detecting dependencies in semi structured data. Solution includes biomedical portal and algorithms (integral rating health criteria, multidimensional data visualization methods). Biomedical portal allows to process diagnostic and research data in parallel mode using Microsoft System Center 2012, Windows HPC Server cloud technologies. Service does not allow user to see internal calculations instead it provides practical interface. When data is sent for processing user may track status of task and will achieve results as soon as computation is completed. Service includes own algorithms and allows diagnosing and predicating medical cases. Approved methods are based on complex system entropy methods, algorithms for determining the energy patterns of development and trajectory models of biological systems and logical-probabilistic approach with the blurring of images

Keywords : Biomedical portal, cloud computing, diagnostic and prognostic research, mathematical data analysis.

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